

Navigating the Tech Wave: Assessing the Impact of Technological Advancements on
Entry-Level Job Requirements

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Abstract: The aim of this paper is to assess the fast-changing nature of technology and its impact on entry-level jobs across. The specific name for this advancement is the fourth industrial revolution, or 'Industry 4.0.' Using a comprehensive methodology that analyzes recent job postings, interviews industry experts, and reviews entry-level job descriptions, the study aims to identify key skills that are increasingly in demand. By focusing on certain industries such as healthcare, manufacturing, and information technology, the research provides practical insights and advice for those preparing for future careers. Furthermore, the paper examines the trend of workers developing new skills in response to rapid technological change and the widespread influence of artificial intelligence. The study shows how technology dynamically changes the requirements for entry-level jobs. It presents a simulation to illustrate how these changes are affecting the workforce, providing a concrete view of the evolving job market.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, jobs, skill force, Industry 4.0, symbiotic, automation, workforce

Methodology: This study adopts a comprehensive literature review approach, analyzing findings from a diverse array of sources to understand the many impacts of artificial intelligence on entry-level jobs. Recognizing the span of the topic, which intersects technology, labor, workforce development, and just everyday life, the methodology is designed to mitigate the risk of biased conclusions. This research is carefully grounded in resources that include peer-reviewed research journals, industry blogs, trusted academic journals, and other online resources. Each source was chosen based on its relevance to this study's themes, author's credibility, and insight on the discussions of AI and employment. For a more balanced view, mixed perspectives are used, including technological, sociological, and economic ones.

With the qualitative nature of this research, the data analysis involved more thematic synthesis. This process means extracting key patterns related to AI's role in changing entry-level job requirements and the bigger consequences. There was extra attention on consensus among sources and areas of divergence were also emphasized. Emerging trends that indicated future direction were also more emphasized. This study acknowledges its reliance on secondary sources as its strength and limitation. This approach does allow for a broad overview of the subject, but it also removes the concept of original data generation. These findings are presented with the interpretation of emphasizing existing literature and our thoughts using this existing literature rather than the generation of new data.

The biggest struggles in navigating the complexities of the 21st century involve the emerging technologies and workforce, which both demand an examination. Artificial intelligence has had many impacts on jobs across all levels, but a more notable impact is the one it has on entry-level jobs. We want to ensure a harmonious integration of AI into the fabric of our professional lives by analyzing everything there is to know. As mentioned before, the term for this changing nature of technology is Industry 4.0.

Industry 4.0 is the modern era in manufacturing that combines digital technology with traditional industrial practices. This era is so different because of the emergence of "smart factories," where machines communicate with each other using the Internet of Things (IoT). But, at the heart of industry 4.0 are technologies like AI and cloud computing. These tools help machines make decisions without human intervention; this leads to a more efficient process. The fourth industrial revolution also has a significant impact on the workforce, demanding new skills and changing the nature of jobs across all industries. Overall, Industry 4.0 is a blend of advanced technology and industrial production, which will create and is creating a whole new era.

Fig. 1 A sample bar graph using different colors to indicate the change in demand for digital skills in U.S. employees

Fig. 1 shows us another way desired skills are changing. As technology evolves, the way we use technology evolves too, which then leads to an increased demand for digital skills. Fig.1 also tells us that 22% of jobs in the U.S. required a high digital score, as of 2014. This number can only have increased from then, but 22% is still considerably high.

Now that we can clearly see that people are getting replaced, let's go a bit deeper. Corporations aren't going to just leave all these college graduates or people starting out their careers without a job, but if they don't need them, what are they going to do? One thing that has been seen is that entry-level job requirements are changing, meaning that more skills are becoming required. The U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics projects a 22 percent growth rate for software developers from 2020 to 2030 (Loftus, 2022). This is a direct correlation between the

skill level a job requires and time, meaning that it is proof that jobs, especially in the software industry, are becoming much harder to qualify for. "The key requirement to reach senior-level engineering roles is the ability to handle even more complex and ambiguous problems, with an understanding of their implications on the business. (Loftus, 2022) " This also shows us that to reach those higher levels, you need that complex problem solving ability. This is the differentiating factor from the entry to high level.

As a result, in a machine-for-machine employment model, low-skilled jobs will disappear, while new and currently unrealized job roles will emerge (Polak 2021)." Picturing a future where this is happening, consider the idea that as AI becomes more sophisticated, the entry-level jobs it could potentially replace may extend beyond routine, repetitive tasks. Entry level jobs may become completely ruled over by AI because it's an easy way to save money. This prompts a crucial question: What defines an entry-level position in a future where basic responsibilities can be automated? It leads us to reevaluate the fundamental skills required for entry-level roles. Entry level jobs might become those jobs that involve those skills we talked about early on. Perhaps, the entry level will require critical thinking and complex problem solving skills, which honestly boils down to the natural talent of the applicants However, this shift also demands a reevaluation of education and training systems. If entry-level positions increasingly require cognitive skills, our educational frameworks must adapt to nurture these abilities from an early stage. This redefined approach to entry-level jobs challenges us to move beyond traditional notions and embrace a paradigm where individuals are selected for their innate capacities rather than task-specific qualifications. What this means is the relationship with humans and AI will turn into something where one compliments the other. The humans bring that creativity and human touch that only humans can, while the AI makes their contributions, whether it be automation or reading data. Entry level jobs would become the gateway to a symbiotic relationship, and this would in turn promote humans to keep on learning.

The employment landscape is undergoing a drastic transformation. As we go to 2025, a staggering 50% of employees are anticipated to undergo reskilling, and by 2027, over two-thirds of today's deemed essential skills are expected to expand. Skills such as negotiation and people management are becoming less and less attractive, while being able to read mass amounts of data to come to a decision is becoming praised. These simple facts facilitate the use of technology rather than using people. In 2025, the top skills are innovation, self-management, critical thinking, complex problem solving, and active learning (Li, 2022). Skills like these are not found in the everyday person, and it goes to show how much technology has changed the standards. Getting a regular education is not enough to have these traits. This is just the very foundation for the need of workforce reskilling. Technology replaces many human traits, but obviously the human touch is still required in many industries, which is why companies want people with skill sets that involve a more complex level of thinking.

Now, that's a lot of information spread across all levels of jobs, but how are the lower level jobs affected? Firstly, entry-level jobs are significantly easier to replace, compared to higher level jobs. Consider the following scenario: A newly hired entry-level coder, despite their determination, finds themselves outperformed by a basic AI model due to the stark contrast in efficiency between the two. Now, some coding projects do require that human touch, but not so much at the lower level. "For instance, IBM has announced plans to replace 8,000 jobs with AI, showcasing a tangible shift towards automation in major corporations" (Wawiwa Tech, 2023). This is just the beginning, the potential of AI is immeasurable. Another example, "The more we use artificial intelligence to do simple tasks like data entry, customer service, and basic analysis, the more likely companies will cease hiring individuals to fill those positions, especially at the entry level" (University of Bridgeport). This means that as AI continues to grow and continues to be used, it will replace more jobs and this hurts the entry-level applicants more than everyone else. "The impact of gen AI alone could automate almost 10 percent of tasks in the US economy. That affects all spectrums of jobs. It is much more concentrated on lower-wage jobs, which are those earning less than \$38,000. In fact, if you're in one of those jobs, you are 14 times more likely to lose your job or need to transition to another occupation than those with wages in the higher range, above \$58,000, for example" (Ellingrud, 2023). 14 times more likely to lose your job.

Fig. 2 A sample bar graph displaying jobs under threat from automation by 2030 in selected countries

Fig. 2 shows us that 400 million workers will be displaced by automation by 2030. This is 15% of the world's working population (in 2030), and we can only imagine the repercussions of something like this. In the United States, it is estimated that 23% of workers will be displaced

by automation. As of right now, reskilling programs are the only way to help soften the blow from these statistics, but is it enough?

Much has been said about how much easier it will be to replace lower level jobs, however there are more specificities involved. Within the lower positions, there are still divisions, like gender and race. “It will affect people of color more. It will affect women more. For instance, women are about 50 percent more likely to be in one of those occupations that needs to transition, compared with men” (Ellingrud, 2023). Specific sectors that traditionally employ a higher percentage of women or people in color such as retail and customer service, are more susceptible to automation. This disproportionate impact underscores the need for targeted interventions and policies that address these inequalities. Training and education programs should be tailored towards the people most at risk. Furthermore, understanding these dynamics is imperative for a more equitable workforce as it encourages the development of inclusive technologies.

Source: Forrester's 2023 Generative AI Jobs Impact Forecast, US

Fig 3. A sample bar graph that shows the number of jobs influenced by AI and number of jobs lost to human generative AI (From 2023-2030)

Fig 3. Shows us a huge incline in both the jobs influenced by AI and the human jobs lost to it . “In 2023 alone, 90,000 jobs are projected to be replaced by ChatGPT and similar generative AI writing tools, representing 9.3% of all automation and AI-related cuts this year.”

Fig.4 A sample stacked bar chart that is color-coded in a way that demonstrates which industries are more susceptible to AI taking over.

Fig 4. How does this phenomenon affect specific industries? Manufacturing and assembly line jobs are already starting to be replaced by automation (the decrease of manual human labor has already started). But, when we talk about transportation and delivery jobs, they haven't been replaced yet. However, this industry is in danger with potential advancements in self-driving cars and drones. Tele-marketing, customer support, which could even include technology support, could also be replaced with automatic calling systems that can handle routine interactions. We see this even in today's job market. Figure 4 shows us that 66 percent of hours worked in banking have the potential to be replaced with AI. That means two-thirds of the hours worked in this industry doesn't even need humans, which is remarkable. The yellow bars on the figure represent the potential of these industries to be replaced by augmentation, which does require human involvement, meaning that all-hope is not lost.

Logically speaking, workforce reskilling and the advancement of skills as a whole is necessary for our society and economy. We all need to learn more to advance. If innovation becomes less prominent, then we won't be able to solve the significant problems seen today. New skills are going to be needed, but new problems will also be created. It is sort of a cycle because as society advances, society gets bigger problems. We have to keep changing, and this means that demands for different products and services will evolve with society. Products and services are used to solve problems, meaning that as problems evolve, so will the solutions.

Fig 5. A sample bar graph that shows the U.S and rural low-skill employment share from 1980 to 2000

Fig 6. A sample bar graph that shows share of global workforce working in low skilled occupations in 2020 and 2030

By comparing these two graphs, we can see that low-skill employment is continuing to decrease. We see that in the 2000's. According to the US census bureau, there was a 35.5% employment share for low-skill jobs. But looking at the more recent graph, under the high-income countries section, it shows an 18% employment share (As of 2020). The number only gets smaller in 2030, showing a declining trend. This once again shows us that the huge majority of the employment share belongs to the high-skill jobs, and this number will only increase as those lower-skill jobs get easier and easier to replace.

As seen in all the figures and analysis, AI does have huge potential to take people's jobs, but it also has the potential to create new ones. Artificial intelligence often requires human oversight and maintenance to do its job properly. The more AI is used in everyday job industries,

the more people needed to oversee it. This could potentially create an entire new category of jobs. The people that are the best at utilizing AI will be at the top of this field. “Instead, we are likely to see new coding jobs that require a different set of skills. For example, there will be greater demand for coders who can design and implement AI systems, integrate AI with existing software, and ensure the security and privacy of AI-powered applications (CodeQuotient, 2023).” This demand not only demonstrates the need for technical expertise, but also shows the importance of interdisciplinary skills, like ethical-decision making.

In conclusion, the influence of artificial intelligence on entry-level jobs is strong and multifaceted. While AI introduces challenges, such as automation-driven job displacement, it also presents opportunities for job transformation and the creation of new roles. The key lies in adaptive strategies—both at the individual and organizational levels—to embrace lifelong learning, skill enhancement, and the integration of AI tools in a manner that augments human capabilities rather than replacing them. This dynamic shift necessitates a collaborative effort among educators, policymakers, and industry leaders to ensure a workforce that is resilient, adaptable, and prepared for the evolving job landscape. Ultimately, the impact of AI on entry-level jobs is not a foregone conclusion of displacement but a call to action for innovation, adaptation, and thoughtful engagement with technology, aiming to harness its potential for the betterment of the workforce and society at large. Entry-level jobs are in danger, many industries are in danger, specific groups of people are in danger; however, there are skills that can make one valuable.

Fig 7. A picture of the in-progress simulation of an entry-level coder versus AI using the Unity Game Engine

When finished, the design promises an immersive and interactive experience.: the user will start the game as an entry-level coder. The game will feature a split-screen layout, the right side of the screen will be an AI model facing off against the user in completing coding tasks. This will be structured as a competitive environment where a central "boss" character. This character will give both the user (the entry-level coder); the AI model a coding task to complete. These tasks can vary from basic algorithms to more complicated things, such as data structures. The simulation will evaluate the speed and quality at which work is completed. The game will also feature a button in the middle; this will allow the user to slow down the AI. This button simulates the real life limits of an AI, such as: absence of creativity, being unable to search for bugs, and resource intensiveness. The ending of the simulation will show a screen presenting the winner of the game (the user or the AI). This will be an extremely realistic representation of the workplace, specific to the coding industry.

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